

Notes

Mossbauer Studies on Some Iron Complexes

V. RAMSHESH* & K. RAVICHANDRAN

Chemistry Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre,
Trombay, Bombay-400085

Manuscript received 3 May 1976, revised 4 September 1976,
accepted 17 November 1976

IN this communication, we report Mossbauer studies on some iron(II) and iron(III) complexes derived from same ligands. The complexes chosen are (i) ferrous and ferric oxinate, (ii) ferrous and ferric diphenyl violuric acid, and (iii) ferrous and ferric diphenyl thiovioluric acid.

Experimental

Ferric oxinate was prepared according to standard methods while the other complexes were supplied by Dr. K. C. Trikha. The Mossbauer spectra were taken on a constant velocity spectrometer^{2,3}. A 2.0 millicurie ⁵⁷CO(Pd) source was used for taking the spectra. The absorbers were made in the form of pellets and mounted on a copper plate using cello tape. For taking spectra at -196°, the copper plate was mounted on a metal crystal and the whole assembly was evacuated.

Results and Discussion

The data on these complexes is shown in Table 1. The chemical shift values have been converted with

TABLE I—MOSSBAUER PARAMETER FOR SOME IRON COMPLEXES

Complex	Temp. (K)	Chemical* shift (mm/sec)	Quadrupole splitting (mm/sec)
Ferric oxinate†	298	0.65	0.80
	78	0.70	0.86
Ferric diphenyl violuric acid.	298	0.61	0.50
	78	0.60	0.45
Ferric diphenyl thiovioluric acid.	298	0.64	0.48
	78	0.66	0.50
Ferrous oxinate**	298	1.27	2.45
Ferrous diphenyl violuric acid.	298	0.72	1.10
Ferrous diphenyl thiovioluric acid.	298	0.68	1.07
	78	0.73	1.10

* with respect to sodium nitroprusside.

** taken from Ref. (4).

† this complex was investigated earlier also by one of the authors.

respect to sodium nitroprusside. For Fe(OX)₃ the values are taken from the data of Steger⁴ for the sake of comparison.

In general the percentage absorption was ~5 to 7% while the line width observed was ~0.50 mm/sec. For a cam driven system such line widths are taken as normal. One of the Mossbauer parameters viz., chemical shift is vastly different for high spin and low spin complexes⁵. Among high spin complexes they are also quite different for divalent and trivalent species of iron. Similarly quadrupole splitting gives an indication of distortion around the metal ion from cubic or spherical charge distribution.

Normally high spin iron(II) complexes show chemical shifts in the range ~0.85 to 1.5 mm/sec (with respect to sodium nitroprusside) though slightly lower values have also been reported in some cases⁶. High spin iron(III) complexes show chemical shifts in the range ~0.40 to 0.70 mm/sec.

Perusal of data in Table 1 shows that all complexes except the ferrous diphenyl violuric acid complexes are of high spin variety with octahedral coordination. The ferrous diphenyl violuric acid complexes show much smaller δ values than expected for spin free state. Magnetic susceptibility measurements for these complexes yield $\mu \approx 5.70$ BM showing the possibility of high spin nature. However, it is not possible to say unequivocally about the nature of these complexes. In the violuric acid complexes the iron is linked to same type of atom while in oxinates the iron is linked to different atoms. The presence of Fe-O and Fe-N bonds in the latter case reduces the molecular symmetry from O_h to C_{2v} thereby causing a large field gradient. This is responsible for larger ΔE values in the oxinates.

Among the complexes in Table 1 only ferrous oxinate seems to be exceptional, showing δ , ΔE values typical of ionic complexes. Steger⁴ has investigated a series of ferrous and ferric oxinates and tried to correlate ΔE values with the difference between the basicity of donor atoms. This was based on the assumption that the strength of Fe-O and Fe-N bonds is related to the basicity of the corresponding donor atom. On the basis of this Steger concluded that the bonding in both Fe(OX)₂ and Fe(OX)₃ is predominantly ionic.

We feel that while in ferrous oxinate the bonding is predominantly ionic, in the case of ferric oxinate it is not possible to distinguish unambiguously the nature of bonding.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. K. S. Venkateswarlu for helpful discussions and Dr. M. D. Karkhanavala, Head, Chemistry Division for the encouragement.

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3-Hydroxypyridine-2-thiol, a Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium

Y. L. MEHTA, B. S. GARG & R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110007

Manuscript received 25 February 1976, revised 21 July 1976,
accepted 26 November 1976

THIOUREA¹⁻³, along with several of its derivatives⁴⁻⁷ has long been used for the spectrophotometric determination of osmium. The complexation between these reagents and osmium is attributed to the presence of a thioketo group (C = S) linked to -NH or -NHR. Recently some more reagents⁸⁻¹¹ have also been suggested for the purpose. Most of the methods suffer from the disadvantage of the interference due to associated platinum metals and require a rigid control of the working conditions. To improve upon the rather limited success of these reagents, in this paper is reported the use of a new reagent 3-hydroxypyridine-2-thiol (HPT), which behaves as a selective and sensitive reagent and allows the determination of osmium(VIII) in micro amounts even in the presence of platinum and other base metals. This reagent (HPT) has already been used for the spectrophotometric and chelatometric determination of iron¹².

In strong hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide media, osmium(VIII) forms with the reagent two complexes, a brown ($\lambda_{\max} = 470$ nm) and a red ($\lambda_{\max} = 520$ nm), both being non-extractable in the commonly used organic solvents. The complexation takes place in cold. The non-interference of EDTA in the colour reaction allows the determination of osmium in the presence of many foreign ions.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents

A Unicam Spectrophotometer SP 600 was used for absorbance measurements and a Metrohm pH

meter was employed for measuring the pH's of the solutions.

A standard solution of osmium(VIII) was obtained from its tetroxide as described by Ayres and Wells¹³, which was further standardized by the method of Klobbie¹⁴. The reagent solution was obtained by dissolving an appropriate quantity in ethanol. This was kept in Corning bottles wrapped in black papers and they were stored in a refrigerator. Standard solutions of other cations were prepared from their chlorides or nitrates and of anions from their sodium or potassium salts; the strengths were determined by conventional methods.

All other reagents were of the highest chemical purity.

Recommended Procedure

To a suitable aliquot of osmium solution, add 2 ml of HPT solution ($10^{-2}M$), adjust the acidity or alkalinity of the solution to 3N and after raising the volume to 10 ml, measure the absorbance of the complexes at the respective $\lambda_{\max}$'s of the complexes using water blanks. Osmium content is determined by comparing it with the standard calibration curves.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance spectra and effect of acidity and alkalinity

The absorption spectra of the system was taken by taking a fixed amount of osmium and excess of reagent solution and varying the pH of solutions to different levels. It was observed that from pH 1-7, a brown complex, exhibiting maximum extinction at 470 nm was obtained. From pH 7-11, a red complex, having $\lambda_{\max}$ at 520 nm was formed. However, no constancy in absorbance could be obtained between these two pH ranges. Hence, the effect of HCl and NaOH concentrations was studied in detail.

It was seen that in case of both complexes the absorbances remains constant and maximum when acidity (for brown complex) and alkalinity (for red complex) ranges are 1-6N HCl and NaOH respectively. Subsequent studies were, therefore, carried out at 3N HCl and 3N NaOH concentrations. Absorption spectra were taken against water blank as the reagent does not absorb at the working wavelengths ($\lambda_{\max}$'s of the complexes).

Effect of heating time and stability

Heating decreases the absorbance of the coloured complexes and was, therefore, avoided. The absorbance of the complexes was found to remain constant for at least 12 hours after which it slowly starts decreasing.

Order of addition of reagents

Variation in the order of the reactants did not have any effect. However, the order followed during the course of investigations is osmium solution, interfering ions (if any), HPT and NaOH or HCl to maintain the required alkaline and acidic conditions.